

developmentSEED

Software Release Plan

Global Fish Tracking System

FOR ESA and Starion
BY Development Seed

VERSION 1.5
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Introduction

This document describes the software release plan for the Global Fish Tracking Software (GFTS) DestinE Platform use case.

Release plan

In the GFTS project we are adopting an agile development and co-design approach. The release plan is therefore something that will evolve as we develop the system and get feedback from stakeholders throughout the process.

At a high level the release plan is informed by the software requirements specification, for which we foresee to release according to the following tentative schedule. The requirements numbers in the table correspond to the items described in the Software Requirement Specification report.

The release schedule includes the points of the three release review meetings, at which the corresponding requirements will be released in their initial version as shown in the timeline of the table.

Requirement ID	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	July
R101	■														
R102	■	■													
R103		■													
R104		■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■					
R105						■	■	■	■	■	■				
R201							■	■	■	■					
R202								■	■	■	■				
R203									■	■	■	■	■		
R204										■	■	■	■	■	■
Review Dates	RR1				RR2							RR3			FR